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ABSTRACTS

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Empowering Treatment Dynamics: n-3 PUFAs Amplify Doxorubicin Efficacy, Halting Proliferation and Invasion in Breast Cancer Cells

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Abstract: Breast cancer remains a prominent cause of global cancer-related deaths among women, marked by unfavorable prognosis and resistance to conventional chemotherapy, notably with doxorubicin (DOXO). Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 PUFAs), vital components of the human diet, exhibit promise in combating breast cancer by targeting malignant cells and impeding tumor progression. Combining n-3 PUFAs, specifically eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), with DOXO presents a compelling strategy to enhance treatment efficacy. Using the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line, this study demonstrated a remarkable increase in cytotoxicity with the combination treatment compared to DOXO alone. Additionally, the combination revealed enhanced suppression of metastasis and a pronounced G1 phase arrest, indicating heightened effectiveness in impeding cell progression. In conclusion, integrating n-3 PUFAs emerges as a potent strategy to augment DOXO's therapeutic potential, effectively curbing the growth and dissemination of breast cancer cells.

Keywords: Breast cancer, n-3 PUFAs, doxorubicin

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